

National Open Access Monitor Project

French Open Science Monitor Meeting, 10th February 2023

Present:

- French Open Science Monitor: Eric Jeangirard, Contributor 1, Contributor 2
- National Open Access Monitor Project Advisory Group: Fran Callaghan; Caleb Derven; Eoin Kenny; Kevin Kiely; Andrew Simpson.
- National Open Access Monitor Project Manager: Catherine Ferris

Agenda: Project plan action "Consult with the providers of the Danish and French national monitoring solutions and create a report which documents their advice, lessons learnt, and methods/tools that could be adapted or reused in the Irish context."

Document Authors: Catherine Ferris, Kevin Kiely, Eoin Kenny

Lessons learnt:

- Built tool layer by layer, initially focused on open access to publications, with simple report/website. Cannot deliver everything from beginning. Need to prioritise.
- Challenge to identify all French publications, to determine which were OA.
- Cannot build everything from the beginning. Step approach. Start small. First started with a poster, then a basic website and today a more advanced website.
- Needed to learn Cloud skills to move from inhouse to public cloud.
- First release included journal articles, conference papers, books, monographs, book chapters. Very few research output types were excluded
- Focus on publications with Crossref DOIs and UnPaywall. Repository/green content represented by Crossref DOIs.
- UnPaywall does not index Crossref and Datacite DOIs the same way.
- Validated that it is possible to build an open science monitor without using proprietary data
- Data quality: take time to look into the results, to ensure they are as expected.
- OpenAire: displayed strange results for France that were not in line with own results as it was initially based on HAL data mainly.
- Machine learning methods have progressed, leverage this instead of proprietary data sources. Especially with regard to finding affiliations, and classification of publications.

- Affiliation metadata is not currently sufficient in open metadata. Algorithms to detect affiliations available on github. OpenAlex may assist with affiliation data now: affiliating to institution rather than country.
- Importance of PIDs: key to build indicators without duplicates. Objects without PIDs are invisible.
- Including publications without DOI, but with HAL ID decreases the OA rate
- UnPaywall snapshots used to identify *change* over open access over time, but not if an article is published immediately open access.
- “Publication date” concept not consistent across sources/metadata. French Open Science Monitor uses UnPaywall publication date.
- Data gathering no reliance on institutions/researchers. Main data sources: UnPaywall (premium API), HAL, OpenAPC, DOAJ. Use DOAJ to determine diamond. Take complete UnPaywall data dump (4 x year) and filter on that.
- Important to be able to remodel data to be to meet national policy requirements (e.g. UnPaywall definition of gold/hybrid/green - prioritises gold/hybrid over green). National Open Science Monitor uses UnPaywall data to show green and diamond articles which are on publisher-hosted too, to enable alignment with policy.

Methods/tools that could be adapted or reused in the Irish context:

- Methodology: <https://hal.science/hal-03651518>
- Open source code: <https://github.com/orgs/dataesr/repositories?q=bs0&type=&language=&sort=>
- Public cloud provider (OVH) to support technical infrastructure.
- External web designer produced wireframes, then developed web app in-house using react

Advice:

Identifying scientific publications countrywide and measuring their open access: The case of the French Open Science Barometer (BSO)

<https://direct.mit.edu/qss/article/3/1/18/109245/Identifying-scientific-publications-countrywide>